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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Translation of the first three pages

**“APPROACH TO SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN
LITERATURES**

Part II: African Literatures in European Languages

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Introduction

As in literary expression in local languages, the thematic and formal diversity of African literary heritage in European languages requires reference to different African literatures. The delimitation of the present work by linguistic areas necessarily entails a certain arbitrariness, due both to the undeniable imprint of colonization and to the fact that division by literary genres is equally debatable, since African authors frequently reformulate their expressions by interweaving drama, poetry, and fiction in countless cases. Nevertheless, solely for the purpose of systematization, it has been preferable to discuss these literatures according to more classical criteria that are more easily comprehensible to the Western reader.

Although the common characteristics of the various African literary manifestations are more numerous—even in European languages—than those that separate them, it is undeniable that each colonized region was deeply influenced by either the so-called policy of assimilation (French, Portuguese, or, to a lesser degree, Spanish) or by the strategy of indirect rule, characteristic of British or Boer governance.

Broadly speaking, it may be said that African literary production in the languages of the colonizers developed in three phases: an initial period in which an authentic expression was forced into the mold of imposed values (the results are often mediocre both in content and from a technical literary standpoint); a second stage in which an impressive mastery of the colonizer's language was achieved, leading to displays of virtuosity and seduction directed at Western audiences; and finally, a third period in which Africa appropriates the foreign language, making it its own and transforming it as necessary so that it may reflect both feeling and lived experience.

In this final phase, African literary manifestations become enriched by local voices and forms of expression. The syntax of the European language is modified so that it adapts to the structure of the mother tongue. As has been said, genres become Africanized, integrating narration and performance into a reinvention whose final result remains unpredictable.

In any case, it should not be forgotten that, beyond the differing circumstances of the continent's peoples, there always persists the same integrating and collective worldview, marked by similar aspirations and ruptures: an Africa that is both one and diverse, an immeasurable arena of Babel, and the final resistance of humanity against the devastating discourse of modernity.

I. POETRY

1. Anglophone Poetry

African Anglophone poetics has always implied a close communion between poet and audience. Toward the end of the 1950s, a tendency toward anthologies can be observed, such as *Africa Centa*, which brought together around one hundred texts already published in the Nigerian press. The tone is moralizing and the technique and style are, in general, somewhat poor.

The situation changes, however, with **Kofi Awoonor** and his *Rediscovery*, in which English serves merely as a medium for expressing experience and Ewe poetry. In Nigeria, the journals *Black Orpheus* and *The Horn*, directed by J.P. Clark and Abiola Irele, would become fundamental to the emergence of an original Nigerian and African poetry.

By contrast, in the 1960s—the first decade of independence—the search for identity takes shape through a new expression that attempts to merge African myth with historical experience. The result is characterized by hermeticism and distances itself from the popular versifiers of previous years. The new poets possess university training and are influenced by T. S. Eliot and Ezra Pound. There is at times a somewhat pedantic effort to demonstrate poetic quality through impeccable command of English. Outstanding among them are **Christopher Okigbo** (*The Gates of Heaven* and *Path of Thunder*) and **Wole Soyinka** (*Idanre*).

By the 1980s, a third generation of Nigerian poets emerged around the University of Ibadan, a movement of vital importance for all of Black Africa. Among these poets, mention should be made of **Odia Ofeimun** (*The Poet Lied*), **Harry Garuba** (*Shadow and Dream*), **Niyi Osundare** (*Songs of the Marketplace* and *Village Voices*), and **Femi Fatoba** (*Petals of Thought*).